

SURVEY ON MALWARE THREATS AND DETECTION TECHNIQUES FOR MOBILE DEVICES

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Abstract:

Smart phones have been increasingly commonplace over the past few years. Personal information like contacts and text messages are stored on mobile devices. Smart phones have grown so widely that cybercriminals are drawn to them. Previous studies on malware protection and detection have concentrated on mitigating the drawbacks of mobile devices' limited capability. Malware for mobile devices can be found using a variety of detection methods, including machine learning, permission-based analysis, dynamic analysis, static analysis, and cloud-based and battery life monitoring. Better anti-mobile malware solutions must be developed in order to get beyond these restrictions, even though detection techniques already exist. Study of well-known approaches currently in use is done as part of the seminar.

I. Introduction

The recently developed mobile devices of today, such as laptops, notebooks, and tablets, are all connected technology. Numerous services, including gaming, entertainment, and the internet, are offered by cell phones through applications. As a result, these gadgets are now an integral part of our daily lives. However, despite the benefits of recently developed technologies, certain security concerns have surfaced.

Mobile Malware: Smartphones are all-purpose handheld computing and communications devices that support multimedia communications and applications for work and play, in contrast to traditional mobile phones, which primarily provide mobile telephony services. The rate at which traditional mobile phones are being replaced with smartphones is phenomenal, owing to this quantum leap in capabilities. Smartphone operating systems include embedded Linux, Android, Symbian, and Palm OS. Because any third-party vendor can develop programmes for Android phones and release them on the Android market, Android is the most popular platform among malware writers targeting smartphones. In the first quarter of 2015, Android smartphones and tablets with Internet connectivity accounted for more than 61% of the global market share. Globally, around 60.85% of users accessed the internet via a mobile device running the Android operating system [1]. Malicious software, sometimes known as malware, is created with the express purpose of damaging or interfering with a mobile device system, like a tablet or smartphone. Malicious software, sometimes known as malware, is created with the express purpose of damaging or interfering with a mobile device system, like a tablet or smartphone. The majority of mobile malware is made with the intention of disabling a mobile device, giving a malevolent user remote access over it, or stealing any personal data that is kept on it. Malicious software, games, and music can be downloaded from various websites onto mobile devices, which is how malware enters the device. Occasionally, during software installation, a number of requests may be made, such as for root access, SMS sending, and internet access. Malware can take control of these rights and utilise them to further its malicious purposes if the user grants them quickly without carefully understanding them. The majority of mobile malware is made with the intention of disabling a mobile device, giving a malevolent user remote access over it, or stealing any personal data that is kept on it.[2]

Mobile Malware Detection Techniques: Numerous methods are employed for detecting mobile malware, including permission-based, dynamic, and static analysis. Additionally, mobile malware detection is accomplished through the use of cloud-based detection and battery life monitoring. Because the classification system is not unique, the methods are broadly categorised into their respective categories.

II. Literature Survey

Static analysis examines a programme that has been downloaded by looking at its source code and software properties. However, software obfuscation and encryption methods make static analysis challenging.

Static analysis was used in Batyuk et al.'s suggested approach for Android applications [8]. First, a thorough static analysis of the applications is conducted, and the user is supplied with intelligible results for evaluation in order to make judgements about installing the applications that are relevant to security. Next, a technique is devised to disable dangerous functionality from programmes, hence mitigating security vulnerabilities.

In order to improve interaction policies and safeguard interfaces between calling and callee applications, On Tang et al.[9] expanded the Android security architecture and introduced the Secure Application Interaction Framework (Saint).

Wei et al.'s [10] devised and created the Droid Mat system, which uses a static feature-based technique to identify and separate Android malware. Static data about components, intents, and permissions is taken into account when describing malware for Android devices. The malware modelling capabilities is improved by applying the clustering technique. Applications are categorised as dangerous or benign using K-Nearest Neighbour techniques. When results are compared, it is discovered that Droid Mat is more effective than Androguard because it predicts 1738 applications in half the time, as reported in Blackhat 2011. by paying attention to the apps' actions' logical sequence.

A behavioural detection framework for representing malware behaviours was presented by Bose et al. [11]. SVM training allows for the differentiation of malicious conduct from regular behaviour. With 96% accuracy, the system is assessed for both simulated and real-world mobile malware. A technique known as centroid, which is based on static function call analysis, was presented by Schmidt et al. [12] for the study of Symbian OS malware. Unknown malware is detected by applying clustering and features taken from binaries. In order to assess user behaviour, Liang et al.[13] gathered data from keyboard logs and LCD displays, developed pBMDS, and then connected the data with system

calls to find unusual activity. In order to identify distinctions between malware and user conduct, hidden markov models, or HMMs, are used to study user behaviour.

PiOS was proposed by Egele et al. [14] to detect leaks of privacy-sensitive data. Decrypting an Objective-C binary and creating a control flow graph that represents the examined application comprise the analysis. The routes that start from resources that are sensitive to privacy and subsequently travel over the network are known as data leak paths. It is determined whether such paths are present in the produced graph. After PiOS was tested on several applications, it was discovered that the majority of them did not commit significant data breaches and that several of them transmitted device IDs without the users' knowledge.

The social collaboration strategy to detection was employed by Yang et al. [15]. The basic idea behind the technique is to share a database of malware signatures across the devices in a social network group of friends in order to minimise the amount of memory used by the malware detection system. They present hot and cold signature sets, each device in a group holding a set of these signatures. This file is downloaded whenever a new one is. The open source anti-malware programme ClamAV serves as the foundation for Social-AV. According to the authors' tests, an AV agent from Social-AV uses roughly 55% of the RAM used by a conventional anti-malware programme with the same level of detection power.

Applications that take advantage of software vulnerabilities are categorised as high-risk by Risk Ranker [16]. Applications are categorised as medium-risk if they steal personal data or cause users to lose money without using software flaws. This tool uses symbolic execution to identify user-intentioned activities and signature-based analysis to identify existing exploits in order to identify programmes that present such dangers. Second-order analysis techniques like native code execution detection, background dynamic code loading, and the usage of encryption and decryption techniques are also implemented by Risk Ranker. When multiple of these characteristics are present in a behaviour, it is deemed high-risk. Table 2.1 provides Summary of Mobile Malware Detection Techniques using Static Analysis

Table 2.1: Mobile Malware Detection Techniques

Proposed Method	Features	Classifier	Result
Bose et al. [11]	Application actions	SVM	on evaluation accuracy is 96 %
PiOS [14]	Keyboard operation and LCD display logs	Hidden Markov Model	possible data leak s825 apps from Apples iTunes store; 582 apps from Cydiastore
Droid Mat [10]	Permissions and application components	Clustering and K-nearest Neighbours	takes half time that of Androguard to predict 1738 apps
Yang et al. [15]	malware signatures	comparison of malware signatures	about 55% of memory consumed by a traditional anti-malware software with the same detection capability
RiskRanker [16]	exploiting software vulnerability	encryption and decryption and Code execution	out of 118,318 apps from a variety of Android markets 718 malware samples in 29 families, including 322 zero-day specimens from 11 distinct families discovered

Dynamic Analysis:

Software tool iDMA was proposed by Damopoulos et al. [25] for dynamic monitoring and analysis of iOS applications. The iDMA CyDetector component can identify particular system calls that can be utilised to get access to a user's confidential information. CyDetector uses a signature-based method of detection. Additionally, the authors used machine learning techniques to assess the monitoring procedures that the app under analysis carried out. Of all the machine learning algorithms put into practice, they observe that the Random Forest algorithm proved to be the most promising. Using a customised version of the Android emulator, the CopperDroid system [26] performs dynamic analysis to trace system calls made by the application. These calls are subsequently handled by the marshalling Oracle component, which retrieves high-level abstractions (IPC or ICC and RPC interactions). To take dependencies between observed system calls into account, the system applies data-flow analysis. In addition, the study involves app stimulation using the malicious behavior-triggering events, which are statically derived from the manifest and application code.

Software tool iDMA was proposed by Damopoulos et al. [25] for the purpose of dynamically monitoring and analysing iOS applications. The iDMA CyDetector component can identify particular system calls that can be utilised to get access to a user's confidential information. CyDetector uses a signature-based method of detection. The monitored methods carried out by the analysed app were analysed by the authors using machine learning approaches as well. They observe that of all the machine learning algorithms put into practice, the Random Forest method proved to be the most promising.

Applications that take advantage of software vulnerabilities are categorised as high-risk by RiskRanker [16]. Applications are categorised as medium-risk if they steal personal data or cause users to lose money without using software flaws. This tool uses symbolic execution to identify user-intentioned activities and signature-based analysis to identify existing exploits in order to identify programmes that present such dangers. Second-order analysis is also implemented by RiskRanker, including the detection of native code execution, background dynamic code loading, and the application of encryption and decryption techniques. When several of these characteristics are present in a behaviour, it is deemed high-risk.

The mechanism that creates application security profiles is called AppProfiler [17]. The authors developed a knowledge base that links API calls to detailed explanations of their privacy-related behaviour and the intended uses of the relevant API. The knowledge database's rules are compared with the API calls that were taken from the decompiled programme. The security profile is then obtained by processing the list of matched rules. Through both an Android application and a web website, AppProfiler allows users to access the profiles.

Yang et al.'s [18] AppIntent is focused on identifying user-intentional disclosures of private information. This step of the method generates an event-space constraint graph with critical events and essential events matching to the necessary preconditions of the critical events. Static taint analysis is performed to determine the paths of privacy-sensitive data propagation and potential leaks. The process of

generating the input data and event chains that result in the transmission of private information is known as guided symbolic execution. The analysed application is repackaged with regard to the aforementioned chains as part of AppIntent, a utility to make the analyst's job easier. The application alerts the user to data leaking, highlights the relevant GUI elements, and automatically repeats the harmful behaviour in accordance with the sequence of events upon execution.

Building behaviour graphs out of the API calls and the relationships between them is part of the analysis done on the DroidSIFT system [19]. Following a comparison of the obtained graphs with the behaviour graphs of benign and malicious programmes, a similarity vector is constructed.

Table 2.2 Malware Detection Techniques using Dynamic Analysis

Proposed Method	Features	Classifier	Result
AA sandbox [20]	APK files, sys-tem calls	Suspicious pat-terns and Mon-key program	150 apps tested and evaluated
Min et al. [21]	Permissions, API calls	LKM	82% apps leak private data out of 350 apps from Amazon andriod market
Rastogi et al. [22]	SMS APIs, kernel level root ploits	fuzzy testing and intelligent black box testing	fuzzy testing and intelligent black box testing
Enck et al.[23]	flow of sensitive information	Specific analysis	Out of 30appstested,15leaks personal information
SmartDroid [24]	Call Graph and Function Call Graph (FCG) and API-calls	fixed-point algorithm	detected the UI-based trigger conditions required to which otherwise cannot be detected with TaintDroid .for 19apps from Antiy and Contagio repository
Damopoulos et al.[25]	system calls	Random Forest algorithm	detected malicious ac- tion accessing users private data iKee-B,iSAM, Messages

Permission-Based Analysis:

Researchers of different stripes are able to identify malicious behaviour in applications by using the rights listed in manifest.xml.[5] Through privacy control and bug and vulnerability reduction, these rights can restrict the behaviour of applications. An architecture for the automatic download of Android applications from the Android Market was proposed by Johnson et al. [27]. Based on its functionality, permissions can be retrieved with static analysis. To find desired permission corrections, the Android source code is searched for permission names, and mapping is done via API calls. With the aid of the programme, each smali file of an application is examined to obtain a list of method calls utilised in the application. Each method call is then checked with the method calls mentioned in the permission-protected Android app to determine the precise permissions. The AndroidManifest.xml file's permission specifications are compared with the restricted permission set. Kirin [28] lays out the requirements for applications' security setups that make them potentially dangerous. If at least one of these requirements is met, Kirin alerts the device owner of a potentially harmful app. These requirements relate to the action strings and requested permissions specified in the manifest file. WHYPER [29] was developed by Pandita et al. to check if the programme has the permissions needed according to its description. The study of descriptions makes use of natural language processing tools. Next, the semantic graphs that reflect the permissions are matched with the parsed descriptions.

Proposed Method	Features	Classifier	Result
Johnson et. al. [27]	permissions and API calls	searching and comparison algorithm	Restricted permission set is compared with all the permissions
Kirin [28]	permissions and action strings	conditions on the security configurations	detected data leaks, disabling antivirus software, SMS spam, control channel through SMS from 311 top apps from Android Market
WHYPER [29]		Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques	581 popular Android apps with an average precision of 82.8%, and an average recall of 81.5% for three permissions

Machine Learning:

Machine learning methods comprise a learning stage where the corresponding detection model is built and a classification stage. The corresponding methods can be regarded as static or dynamic analysis methods using machine learning as a tool.[30] Aafer et al. [31] proposed DroidAPIMiner performs analysis in two steps.Firstly, analysis of the bytecode is done.A vector of the used On this stage, APIs are created. After that, classification is carried out using one of the classifiers listed below: ID5 DT, C4.5 DT, KNN, or SVM. The KNN classifier yielded the best results. At least 6% more malicious applications use these API calls than benign ones do. The permission model did not seem to be sufficiently resilient when applied to the applications requiring permissions that did not use the training dataset, despite the fact that Aafer et al. also employed the vectors of required permissions for the classification. The MAST application triage method was presented by Chakradeo et al. [32] in an effort to reduce the expenses and resources needed to stop malware in expansive application marketplaces.

The system's primary goal is to find the most dubious applications so that they can be thoroughly examined. The writers take out programme features including native code, embedded zip archives, and needed permissions and intent filters. Next, Multiple Correspondence Analysis is used to calculate the similarity between the examined application and the malicious application groupings. The application danger's general rank is calculated using the values that were acquired. Utilising text mining methods, Dendroid [33] examines the applications' code structure. Initially, code fragments are extracted by the authors using the Androguard tool from a group of malicious programmes. Next, using the term frequency-inverse document as a foundation, frequency statistics family feature vectors are constructed. The highest values in the feature

vector are assigned to code segments that are most distinctive to a family of malware. Malware families and related feature vectors are then studied in more detail using hierarchical cluster and linkage studies. When an application is evaluated for the first time, Dendroid finds the malware family whose vector, measured by the cosine similarity score, most closely resembles its feature vector.

Table 2.4 Mobile Malware Detection Techniques using Machine Learning

Proposed Method	Features	Classifier	Result
Aafer et al. [31]	API calls and Package Level Information	ID5 DT, C4.5 DT, KNN, SVM	detected 8987 malicious apps with an accuracy as high as 99% and a false positive rate as low as 2.2% using KNN classifier.
Dendroid [33]	code structure	Hierarchical clustering technique	detected malware family for malicious samples from Android Malware Genome Project
Chakradeo et al [32]	specific required permissions and Intent filters, embedded zip-archives, the presence of native code	Multiple Correspondence Analysis	predicted rank of the danger for 36710 apps from Soft Android

III. Methodology

Techniques for static analysis examine an application's content without using its execution or emulation. Decompiling is frequently the initial stage of analysis, after which data structures representing the characteristics of an interest are constructed.[30] By scalably and accurately sorting through the vast number of untrusted apps in the current Android markets, including both official and unofficial ones, RiskRanker [16] is a proactive technique to identify zero-day Android malware. Our scheme is motivated and appropriately built to quantify potential security dangers provided by these untrusted apps, without relying on malware specimens (and their signatures). The possible hazards are divided into three groups: high-, medium-, and low-risk. Without the necessary consent from users, high-risk apps leverage platform-level software flaws to damage the integrity of phones.

Figure 3.1: The Risk Ranker Architecture

While medium-risk apps don't take advantage of software flaws, they nonetheless have the potential to cost users money or reveal private information. For instance, these applications might secretly sign users up for premium services. Similar, but gentler, are low-risk apps, which may gather generic, widely accessible personal data or device-specific data. The first-order analysis modules are made to be scalable in order to identify high- and medium-risk applications by sifting through untrusted apps. DroidRanger [4] classifies a programme as malicious or benign by combining static and dynamic analysis techniques. The next step is to identify any malware infection among them.

Figure 3.2: DroidRanger Architecture

WHYPER [29] is a framework for figuring out why an application utilises a permission by applying Natural Language Processing (NLP) approaches. WHYPER evaluates which language (if any) in an application's description signals the use of permission by using a semantic.

Figure 3.3: Overview of WHYPER Framework

A cloud-based malware protection technique called Paranoid Android was proposed by Portokalidis et al. [34]. A tracer captures all the information required to repeat the execution of a programme over the phone. The authors demonstrate the practicality and detection of zero-day attacks with their implementation of devolved attack detection for Android G1 phones. The architecture scales in detection methods: many detection methods can be run in parallel (including expensive ones), with zero overhead on the phone for each additional method.

Figure 3.4: Paranoid Android Architecture Overview

To be more precise, they used a specialised security server to run a synchronised clone of the phone. Security checks that would be too costly to do on the phone itself can be carried out on the server because it does not have the strict resource limitations that a phone does. In order to do this, a limited trace of the phone's operation—just enough to allow for replay—is recorded and sent to the server. PA offers strong attack visibility and scalability in terms of the number and range of detection methods. They used transparent backup to safeguard user data, making it impossible for attackers to conceal their footprints.[34] These characteristics are required for next-generation cell phones to have strong security. Transmission overhead can be kept far below 2.5KiBps after compression even during periods of heavy activity (browsing, audio playback), and to almost nothing during idle periods, according to the evaluation of a user space implementation of our architecture, Paranoid Android. About 30% less battery life is achieved, but it has been demonstrated that by integrating the tracer into the kernel, battery life can be greatly increased.[14]

IV Result and Discussion

Every technique covered in the Methodology chapter has been chosen to be a sample example in each category. Table 4.1 discusses the observed results. RiskRanker [16] looked at 118, 318 apps that were gathered from various Android stores throughout the two months of September and October 2011. Processing this many apps with RiskRanker takes less than four days. It finds that out of the 3281 suspicious apps it reports, 718 dangerous apps (from 29 malware families) have 322 zero-day vulnerabilities (in 11 separate families). After applying DroidRanger [4] to the gathered apps, our system was able to identify 211 dangerous apps. Of them, this heuristic-based filtering strategy finds two very advanced zero-day malware strains. In the official Android Market, there are eleven of them. To highlight permission sentences, the WHYPER [29] framework presently just looks at Android API documentation and application descriptions. Therefore, a framework can list the uses of a licence in a semi-formal manner. Future searches for desired applications can be improved with the use of this information.

V: Conclusion

These days, mobile devices are offering an increasing number of computer-like features. As a result, fresh security risks like mobile malware have surfaced. There are numerous methods available for detecting malware. Even so, there are certain shortcomings with these methods. After examining these methods, it is discovered that several analysis techniques can be combined to enhance the outcomes of detection. For example, using a cloud-based approach can lessen the strain on the device. Additionally, network traffic analysis and API call monitoring offer more useful data for malware detection. The ratio of malware detection could be enhanced using artificial intelligence and machine learning methods. The RiskRanker [17] prototype shows encouraging results when using the static analysis method; nonetheless, it is still a proof-of-concept system and has a number of significant shortcomings. Since the root exploit detection method relies on signatures, it is evident that it can only identify known exploits and may overlook ones that have been encrypted or disguised. The second-order risk analysis makes things better and seems to be working really effectively right now. However, if such techniques start to hinder the deployment of malware in app markets, malware authors might respond by attacking some of the assumptions that make this method work so well. For example, this prototype only considers the `javax.rpyt` libraries for convenient encryption detection; nothing prevents an attacker from implementing their own in-app encryption or decryption scheme. Similarly, instead of packaging their native code in the assets or resource directories, such code could be included as large constant arrays in the Dalvik binary itself. While it is possible to counter all of these strategies, it is obvious that the situation can and likely will grow more complicated as malware matures on the platform. In Dynamic analysis, DroidRanger [4] the scanning

results show a relatively low malware infection rate on studied Android Markets. But if these tactics begin to impede the spread of malware in app stores, malicious developers may counter by challenging some of the underlying presumptions that enable this strategy to function so effectively. For instance, nothing stops an attacker from developing their own in-app encryption or decryption technique; this prototype just takes into account the `javax.rpytolibraries` for easy encryption detection. Similarly, similar code might be incorporated as big constant arrays in the Dalvik binary itself, rather than packaging its native code in the resource or assets directories. Even while each of these tactics may be avoided, it is clear that as malware on the platform develops, things could and probably will become more difficult. The scanning results in DroidRanger's dynamic analysis [4] indicate a comparatively low malware rate. They have both techniques implemented in DroidRanger, and the evaluation results show that our methodology is both feasible and effective as they effectively detect 211 dangerous apps and unearth two zero-day viruses in both official and unofficial marketplaces. Despite this, a thorough screening procedure is necessary to more effectively police both legal and illegitimate marketplaces. Recognitions The writers hope to WHYPER [29] framework currently only uses application descriptions and Android API documentation to highlight permission sentences in permission-based analysis. As a result, the permissions' uses can be semi-formally listed by the framework. In the future, this information can be used to improve the process of looking for desired applications. Moreover, our framework's results could be used with programme analysis methods to enable efficient code reuse. For example, the framework outputs the justifications for why an application needs permission. These justifications are typically related to the features that the application offers.

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